

Aligned Structure of Copper-Indium Eutectoidal Composite

K. Shinohara¹⁾, I. Ueda²⁾, T. Seo¹⁾, S. Umekawa³⁾

- 1) Department of Metallurgy, School of Engineering, Ehime University, 3 Bunkyo-machi, Matsuyama 790, Japan
- 2) Department of Physics, School of General Education, Kyushu University, 4-2-1 Ropponmatsu, Chuo-ku, Fukuoka 810, Japan
- 3) Research Laboratory of Precision Machinery and Electronics, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Nagatsuda, Midori-ku, Yokohama 227, Japan

ABSTRACT

Cu-In alloys of eutectoidal composition was allowed to transform unidirectionally at various rates, obtaining eutectoidal composites consisting of alternate layers of α and δ - phases. Examinations were made on two different aspects. The unit cell of the δ -phase was determined by X-ray diffraction to be: $a=0.9028$ $b=1.005$ and $c=0.669$ nm with their glancing angles of $\alpha=97.29$, $\beta=90.28$ and $\gamma=73.26$ degrees, where a, b, c and α, β, γ , are conventionally defined. This crystal belongs to a triclinic system of the space group of $P1$ or $P\bar{1}$. Secondly, the morphological variation of the layers as a function of cooling rate was examined. The layers of α and δ -phases are in an alternately ordered state at slow rate of the transformation whereas they are disordered and often terminated at the increased rates. The interlamellar spacing, λ , and the rate of transformation, v , gave a relationship $\lambda^{3.8}v = \text{constant}$ which agrees closely with the proposal made by Carpay. Furthermore, the hardness is found to satisfy the Hall-Petch relationship.

INTRODUCTION

One of the common methods to prepare a composite material having a well aligned microstructure is to allow a eutectic mixture to solidify unidirectionally, thereby obtaining alternate layers of hard and soft materials brought into contact.⁽¹⁻³⁾ Only recently, however, has it become possible to produce a lamellar structure by unidirectional decomposition of a solid phase.⁽⁴⁻¹¹⁾ The techniques used in eutectic solidification and in eutectoid reactions are similar. Previous investigations deal with the morphological variation of the reaction products and the interlamellar spacings, λ , as a function of a growth rate, v ,⁽⁴⁻⁹⁾ and the crystallographic orientation relationship between the two phases in contact.⁽¹⁰⁾⁽¹¹⁾

A fundamental theory which is applicable to eutectic reactions has first been developed by Jackson and Hunt,⁽¹²⁾ obtaining the re-

relationship $\lambda^n v = \text{constant}$ with $n=2$. This relationship has been generally proved to be valid for eutectic reaction products⁽²⁾ but it is accepted only in limited number of eutectoidal reaction products⁽⁹⁾. In the case of eutectoidal decomposition, theories giving $n=3$ and 4 have been proposed. Zener⁽¹³⁾ originally examined the pearlite reaction and derived a relationship between growth rate and supercooling on the basis of volume diffusion. Turnbull⁽¹⁴⁾, however, suggested grain boundary diffusion instead of volume diffusion as a governing mechanism of lamellar growth. Cahm⁽¹⁵⁾, Shapiro and Kirkaldy⁽¹⁶⁾, Sundquist⁽¹⁷⁾, and Carpay and van den Boomgaard⁽⁶⁾ made theoretical treatments for eutectoid reactions, all of which are based on grain boundary diffusion. These theories predict $n=3$ rather than 2. Carpay et al.⁽⁶⁾, on the other hand, derived the relationship with $n=4$ on the basis of the role of kinetic supercooling in the solid state transformation process. As a whole, the theory of growth of lamellae in eutectoid reactions is still controversial.

Experiments on Cu-In eutectoid system made by Carpay^(5,6) give a result of $n=3.7$, proving his theoretical postulate that gives $n=4$. Toriumi⁽⁷⁾ investigated the growth law for Cu-Al eutectoid, obtaining the result that the value of n depends on the growth rate; at increased velocity, $n=1.2$ results whereas at decreased velocity $n=3.7$ results.

Cu-In eutectoid system has not been extensively investigated. One of the reasons for this is presumably that the crystal structure of the δ -phase is not known. Fig. 1 shows the phase diagram of Cu-In system.⁽¹⁸⁾ Clearly this alloy has a eutectoid reaction at 847K. The γ -phase which is stable at temperatures higher than 847 K decomposes into α -solid solution and δ -phase having a composition of Cu_9In_4 . The crystal structure of this phase is variously described. Weibke and Eggers⁽¹⁹⁾ report that it is cubic while Hellner and Laves⁽²⁰⁾ state that it is hexagonal, having NiAs type structure. Furthermore, Reynolds et al.⁽²¹⁾ propose that it is tetragonal. Without the knowledge of crystal structure, it is unable to find the crystallographic relationship between α and δ -phases, the reaction products of the Cu-In eutectoidal decomposition.

Here, attempts were made to determine the crystal structure of the δ -phase and to find the features in morphology and alignment of the Cu-In eutectoidal constituents produced by unidirectional decomposition.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimens were prepared by melting copper of 99.99% purity and indium of 99.97% purity having nominally a eutectoid composition in an encapsulated silica tube whose inner diameter was 3 mm. The silica tube containing copper and indium had been evacuated to the order of 4×10^{-6} Pa. The silica tube was first heated at 1373K for 10h to melt and homogenize the samples, and subsequently quenched into water. The quenched sample presumably homogeneous in composition was fixed along the path of a moving electric resistance furnace. An attempt was made to produce a steep temperature gradient by water cooling at one end of the furnace. The overall view of the setup is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2. The temperature gradient measured in the furnace was 100K/cm at the eutectoid temperature of 847K. The rate of upward movement of the furnace was variously changed ranging from 0.22 $\mu\text{m/s}$ (0.8mm/h) to 10.6 $\mu\text{m/s}$ (3.8cm/h). The microstructure of the samples thus grown unidirectionally was examined by the scanning electron microscope of the type SHIMAZU ASM-Sx.

The analysis of the crystal structure of δ -phase was made by the well established four circle diffractometer from 25 reflections.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Crystal Structure Determination

At first, the uniformity of the chemical composition of the specimen was examined by the scanning electron microscope at five different locations. It was found that the specimen was uniform in composition having Cu_9In_4 within 2% of an error. This confirmed that this specimen consisted indeed of the δ -phase. With use of the diffractometer, the cell constants were determined as following $a=0.908$, $b=1.005$ and $c=0.669$ nm and their glancing angles of $\alpha=97.29$, $\beta=90.28$ and $\gamma=73.26$ degrees. This crystal structure belongs to a triclinic system having a space group of $P1$ or $P\bar{1}$. The unit cell was found to contain three atoms. This crystal structure found here is different from any of those reported previously.

Fig. 3 shows an example of transmission electron micrographs taken from the eutectoid structure. Its diffraction pattern could be successfully indexed. Thus, the crystal analysis by x-ray diffraction is consistent with that by transmission electron microscopy.

Unidirectionally Transformed Microstructures

Fig. 4 shows the variation of microstructures of the specimens which have been allowed to transform unidirectionally at different furnace velocities. The microstructures of longitudinal and transverse sections are demonstrated, respectively, on the left and right sides. The growth rate is the slowest in the uppermost picture and the fastest in the bottom. The white area in the figure is found by the scanning electron microscope to correspond to the δ -phase and the dark area to α -solid solution of copper containing indium. From the morphology of longitudinal and transverse sections, it is apparent that these alternate layers of α and δ phases are plate-like. The degree of alignment is improved by decreasing growth rate. In addition, on increasing the growth rate the plate-like phase tend to bend and termination of δ -phase takes place more often in quickly grown than in slowly grown specimens. When the growth rate is beyond $4 \mu\text{m/s}$, not only the parallelism of layers but also the continuation of the δ -phase are lost due to the terminations stated above. In order to have a non-crippled form of the δ -phase, the rate of transformation had to be less than $3 \mu\text{m/s}$ in the case of Cu-In eutectoid reaction. This critical rate is much smaller in eutectoid than in eutectic reactions.⁽⁵⁾ Since the alignment is established by the diffusion of solute atoms it is much faster in the liquid than in the solid state. Fig. 5 shows different areas of the same specimen shown in Fig. 4. Even in the slowly transformed specimen, the termination can be seen at several spots. In a quickly transformed specimen, a lot of directional misalignment occur, whose angular deviations do not seem to be random but to be related with some crystallography. The latter structure is often referred to as a "herring-bone structure".⁽⁶⁾⁽⁷⁾ The mechanism of forming the herring-bone structure is still in dispute. One ascribes it to the fluctuation of thermal flow within a specimen, another to the twin-oriented growth and the other to the growth onto crystallographically equivalent planes and directions.⁽⁷⁾ The formation of the herring-bone structure is more likely to occur in quickly transformed specimens.

In Fig. 6 is plotted the interlamellar spacing, λ , as a func-

tion of the growth rate, v . The linearity is obvious, giving the value of $n=3.8$ which is in close agreement with the proposal by Carpay.⁽²²⁾ In Fig. 7 is shown the relationship between Vickers hardness and interlamellar spacings. The linearity between hardness and square root of λ indicates the validity of the Hall-Petch relationship. From these results, one can conclude from a strengthening standpoint that there should be a compromise for a favorable eutectoidal composite between the fast transformation rate giving rise to small interlamellar spacings which results in strengthening and the increased tendency to obtain the crippled form of the hard phase embedded in a soft matrix which may not be effective in strengthening because of the decreased aspect ratio.⁽²³⁾

CONCLUSIONS

Following conclusions have been drawn from this investigation:

(1) The crystal structure of the δ -phase in Cu-In alloy has been determined: it belongs to a triclinic system of a space group $P1$ or $P\bar{1}$. Its unit cell is described as follows.

$a=0.908(\text{nm})$	$\alpha=97.29(\text{in degrees})$
$b=1.005$	$\beta=90.28$
$c=0.669$	$\gamma=73.26$

(2) The morphology of Cu-In eutectoidal composite varies as it is allowed to transform unidirectionally at different rates. The slow rate of the transformation gives the ordered alternate layers of α and δ phases with slight tendency to form the termination of the layer and with the great interlamellar spacings, whereas the quick rate of the transformation gives the increased tendency to yield the crippled morphology of the layers.

(3) In order to obtain an alternate layer in well-aligned morphology, a eutectoidal composite must be transformed at much slower rate than eutectic composite, since the morphology is governed by the diffusion of each atomic species and it is much faster in a liquid than in a solid.

(4) The relationship between interlamellar spacings and the rate of the transformation was linear in a logarithmic scale, giving the value of $n=3.8$ for the equation written as $\lambda^n v = \text{constant}$. This agrees closely with the proposal made by Carpay.⁽⁵⁾

(5) Hardness of the composites and the interlamellar spacings satisfy the Hall-Petch relationship. From a strengthening standpoint, there is a compromise in the rate of transformations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to our colleague, in particular Messrs. K.Kamiki and T.Kamano in our laboratory at Ehime University for making efforts in pursuing experiments and in preparing this manuscript.

REFERENCES

(1) Piatti, G., "Preparation of New Multiphase Composites," Proc. of Internl. School of Physics, Course 61, ed. by Gaglioti, G., 1976, North-Holland, New York, pp. 602-648

- (2) Davies, I.G. and Hellowell, A., "The Structure of Directionally Frozen Al-CuAl₂ Eutectic Alloy", *Phil. Mag.*, vol.19, 1969, pp.1285-1297
- (3) Chilton, J.P. and Hunt, J.D., "An Investigation of the Lamella-Rod Transition in Binary Eutectics", *J. Inst. Met.*, vol.91, 1962, pp.338-342
- (4) Carpay, F.M.A., "Lamellar Eutectoid Growth", *Acta Met.*, vol.20, 1972, pp.929-934
- (5) Carpay, F.M.A., "The Preparation of Aligned Composite Materials by Unidirectional Solid-State Decomposition", *Acta Met.*, vol.18, 1970, pp.747-752
- (6) Carpay, F.M.A., and van den Boomgaard, J., "The Relationship between Interlamellar Period and Growth Rate in the Unidirectionally Decomposed Eutectoids Co₃Si and Ni-In", *Acta Met.*, vol.19, 1971, pp.1279-1286
- (7) Toriumi, H., Terasawa, S. and Izumi, O., "The Study of Unidirectional Transformation of Copper-Aluminium Eutectoid Alloy Controlled by the Heat Flow", *J. Inst. Metals Japan*, vol.41, 1977, pp.657-663
- (8) Carpay, F.M.A., "On the Eutectoid Reaction in Cu-Al and Fe-C", *Met. Trans.*, vol.5, 1974, pp.2614-2615
- (9) Bolling, G.F. and Richman, R.H., "Forced Velocity Pearlite", *Met. Trans.*, vol.1, 1974, pp.2095-2104
- (10) Rao, P., Livingston, J.D., and Koch, E.F., "Crystallography of Aligned Copper-Aluminium Eutectoid", *Acta Met.*, vol.22, 1974, pp.1513-1519
- (11) Pitsch, W., "Der Orientierungszusammenhang zwischen Zementit und Ferrit in Perlit", *Acta Met.*, vol.10, 1962, pp.79-80
- (12) Jackson, K.A. and Hunt, J.D., "Lamellar and Rod Eutectic Growth", *Trans. AIME*, vol.236, 1966, pp.1129-1142
- (13) Zener, C., "Kinetics of the Decomposition of Austenite", *Trans. AIME.*, vol.167, 1946, pp.550-583
- (14) Turnbull, D., "Theory of Cellular Precipitation", *Acta Met.* vol.3, 1955, pp.55-63
- (15) Cahn, J.W., "The Kinetics of Cellular Segregation Reaction" *Acta Met.*, vol.7, 1959, pp.18-28
- (16) Shapiro, J.M., and Kirkaldy, J.S., "Theory of Decomposition of Eutectoids Assuming Local Equilibrium and Phase Boundary Diffusion", *Acta Met.*, vol.16, 1968, pp.579-585
- (17) Sundquist, B.E., "The EdgeWise Growth of Pearlite", *Acta Met.*, vol.16, 1968, pp.1413-1427
- (18) Hansen, M., and Anderko, K., Constitution of Binary Alloys, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1958, pp.590
- (19) Weibke, F. und Eggers, H., "Das Zustandsdiagramm des Systems Kupfer-Indium", *Z. anorg. Chem.*, vol.220, 1934, pp.273-292
- (20) Hellner, E. und Laves, F., "Kristalchemie des In und Ga in Legierungen mit Einigen Übergangselementen (Ni, Pt, Cu, Ag, und Au)", *Z. Naturforsch.*, A2, 1947, pp.177-183
- (21) Reynolds, J., Wiseman, W.A., and Hume-Rothery, W., "The Equilibrium Diagram of the System Copper-Indium in the Region 25-35 at. % Indium", *J. Inst. Met.*, vol.80, 1952, pp.637-641
- (22) Petch, N.J., Progress in Metal Physics, ed. by Chalmers, B. and King, R., vol.5, Pergamon, London, 1954, 1
- (23) Christensen, R.M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1979, 73

Fig. 3 Electron Micrograph of (a) Bright Field Image Showing the Plate-Like δ -Phase and (b) Its Selected Area Diffraction Pattern. (c) Is the Key Diagram of the Indexed Pattern with the Knowledge of Its Crystal Structure.

(a) $0.22 \mu\text{m/s}$

(b)

(a) $1.22 \mu\text{m/s}$

(b)

(a) $3.06 \mu\text{m/s}$

(b)

Fig.4 Aligned Structure of Cu-In Eutectoidal Composite Cooled at Different Rates (a) Longitudinal and (b) Transverse Sections.

0.22 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$

1.22 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$

Fig. 5 Cu-In Eutectoidal Composite with Longitudinal Section Aligned in Parallel with a Growth Direction

Fig. 6 Logarithmic Plot of Interlamellar Spcing, λ vs. Growth Rate, v .

Fig. 7 Hardness as a Function of Square Root of Interlamellar Spacings, Showing the Validity of Hall-Petch Relationship.